

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Automatic Melodic Harmonization from Symbolic Melody Using BLSTM Networks

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Dedication

I would like to dedicate this work to my family and friends who supported me throughout this endeavour.

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I would like to thank the following people who have helped me undertake this master thesis:

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Abstract

Producing chord progressions from a melody is a challenging task for multiple reasons but mainly because harmonic subtleties are difficult to describe computationally. In this work, we will address the problem of automatic melodic harmonization and we will attempt to provide a proof of concept of generating chord progressions using bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTM) networks from symbolic melodies. A dataset of lead sheets of various music genres will be used to extract meaningful melodic and harmonic information. To achieve uniformity of data, each track of the dataset will be transposed to either C major or C minor according to its initial key signature, while time signature will be normalized to avoid the imbalance of note durations. The result of the extraction will compose two-dimensional arrays consisting of twelve-note classes representing single notes in a sequence of four bars. After the pre-processing of data, the BLSTM network will be trained to generate chord progression vectors of four bars as output and its accuracy will be measured. Finally, a quantitative evaluation will take place where the model will be compared with other state-of-the-art algorithms to observe their performance.

Keywords: automatic melodic harmonization; chord generation

Chapter 1

Introduction

Automatic melodic harmonization, in general, is the task of trying to accompany a melody with chords. A melody is a group of notes played one after the other and harmony, one would suggest, is the process of creating simultaneous notes that satisfy or accompany the melody. Usually, it obeys a certain rule system like western harmony. We could say that in the case of this work, automatic melodic harmonization means the generation of chords to accompany a melody.

Generally, the task is commonly performed manually by musicians and music experts. It is a quite common task in the study of harmony. However, with the advent of computers, all the harmonic rules can be analyzed and simulated by frameworks. The practice of abstracting rules of harmony and placing them in a linguistic framework has been a part of computer science at least since the 1960s and the task of automatic melodic harmonization is a natural extension of harmonic analysis. It is considered a part of algorithmic music composition and various systems have been developed to perform it.

In this work a disclaimer should be added, declaring that our approach is based on chord sequence generation and not harmonization of notes one by one mainly because the way the dataset functions is by providing chords on a bar basis where we can't increase the grain of the chords on our own as we can do manually. Therefore, there's a difference between automatic melodic harmonization and the generation

for example of Bach chorales. A visual explanation can be seen in 1.

Automatic Melodic Harmonization	Chorale

Figure 1: On the left, the form of automatic melodic harmonization in our work and on the right an example of Bach’s chorale where melodic harmonization if performed in the traditional way of western harmony.

1.1 Motivation

The study of harmony (in a classical western context) is a necessary process for the emergence of a new musician. It involves the analysis and understanding of the harmonic principles in a deeper level and the construction of meaningful chord progressions that fulfil the purpose of the melody. By studying harmony at the conservatoire I realized the importance of the task while at the same time I was interested in its automation. During this masters, it came to my attention how common automatic melodic harmonization is in research since the beginning of algorithmic music and as a result, I was intrigued by the state of the art practices attempting to solve it.

1.2 Repository

The code of this master thesis can be found at the following repository:

<https://github.com/myrsini-io/AutomaticMelodicHarmonization>

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Algorithmic Composition

Over the years there have been developed many definitions about what algorithmic composition is. According to Cope (1993), algorithmic composition is "a sequence (set) of rules (instructions, operations) for solving (accomplishing) a [particular] problem (task) [in a finite number of steps] of combining musical parts (things, elements) into a whole (composition) " [1]. Alpern (1995) defines algorithmic or "automated" composition as "the process of using some formal process to make music with minimal human intervention" [2] while Nierhaus (2009) simply describes it as "composing by means of formalizable methods". In spite, all of the definitions that academics suggested, a self-explanatory and literal approach might be an accurate yet a simple solution to the question 'what is algorithmic composition?'...the use of algorithms to compose music [3].

2.2 Historical Presentation of Algorithmic Composition

2.2.1 Pre-Computer Era

Algorithmic composition is not a recent invention or a product of the last decades as its name suggests. Even though the term “algorithm” is correlated with computer science which has grown rapidly over the last century, composing music using algorithms is not strictly exclusive to the use of computers. For centuries, composers have been taking advantage of algorithms to enhance their creative process or to formalize it, although computers have provided them with new possibilities and liberties. The first steps were made possibly by Pythagoras in ancient Greece (500 BC) who was convinced that mathematics and music are related and this relationship resulted in harmony [4]. Also, Plato (400 BC) provided the concept of *musica Universalis* that is music derived from the movement of the planets. Similarly, Ptolemy (150 AD) believed that there was a correlation between certain notes and celestial bodies [4]. These notions are not considered algorithmic but are important in terms of history for the formalization of composition. An early approach to algorithmic composition took place by music theorist Guido of Arezzo (1000 AD) who developed a new notation system for the automatic generation of melodies out of text [1]. Shortly after his period, the motet arose as the main form of polyphonic whose complexity increased significantly. As a result, further developments of notation occurred like a mensural notation in the 13th century which is a system that gives notes rhythmic durations [1]. In the 15th century, the canonic composition provided a new framework of imitation rules that could be considered algorithmic [4]. Furthermore, Athanasius Kircher, a polymath and scholar, designed an algorithmic composition system for counterpoint around 1650 AD that was very significant in terms of algorithmic thinking. Another example of automatic generation of music was a game that became popular in Western Europe during the 18th century and can be found in the works of many composers during this period. The game was called *Musikalisches Würfelspiel* in which dices were used to generate pre-composed

music pieces that were combined by chance [4]. In addition, another game regarding systems that enabled automatic generation of music was a set of cards called “the Quadrille Melodist “. It was manufactured by Professor J. Clinton of the Royal Conservatory of Music in London around 1856 BC and could generate 428 million quadrilles of music [5]. After the Second World War, a revolution in music composition happened that was crucial for algorithmic composition too. In 1923 Arnold Schoenberg introduced his twelve-tone technique. This method of composing was a system for creating music generatively, by using one note of the chromatic scale at a time that could not be reused until all the remaining notes have been utilized. In that way, an emphasis given on one specific note was prevented and the equal importance of all notes was established. The substitution of decisions over pitch structure with a series of values resulted in an automated way of composition, by eliminating or minimizing the choices of the composer [4]. The technique was adopted by many composers in the 20th century and is considered a form of serialism. Over the next decades, several radical systems that can be classified as algorithmic composition techniques were implemented without the use of computers. For instance, John Cage used randomness in his music that was triggered by a performer’s movement, thus each performance was transformed into a unique experience. Finally, Ligeti even though he is not associated with algorithmic composition, was inspired by science and mathematics and experimented with deterministic algorithmic thinking [6] in his piece *Désordre*.

"Somewhere underneath, very deeply, there’s a common place in our spirit where the beauty of mathematics and the beauty of music meet. But they don’t meet on the level of algorithms or making music by calculation. It’s much lower, much deeper—or much higher, you could say."

-Ligeti [6]

The complexity of the new compositional techniques of the last century made appealing their implementation in computer software that took place ultimately, with the advance of computers [5].

2.2.2 Computer Era

In the mid-1950s, the appearance of computers expanded the horizons of algorithmic composition even though their processing power was limited, their cost was high and they were very complicated to use. One of the most famous and earliest examples of a composition that was generated using computers is that of Hiller and Isaacson at the University of Illinois [3] [4]. In 1957 they used rule systems and Markov chains to generate *Illiac Suite* that took its name from the computer that they were using. After the generation of the score by the computer, the piece was transposed into traditional musical notation to be performed by a string quartet [4]. As a result, this model was applied to a later project in the late 50s by Hiller and Bacewicz, *MUSICOMP*. This project was a collection of subroutines that was popularized in many algorithmic composition systems because of its efficiency and flexibility [4]. Furthermore, the potentiality of Hiller's system was acknowledged by John Cage, resulting in their cooperation in 1969 on a stochastic project. *HPSCHD* was a randomly generated piece that used Mozart and other composers as a foundation to form the composition [5]. The history of algorithmic composition is divided into two different methodologies, stochastic and deterministic [5]. In stochastic methodologies, random procedures take place for example in Markov chains. In deterministic methodologies, algorithms that imply rules, define the results of the systems. Xenakis was an engineer and pioneer of algorithmic composition who applied stochastic processes in his compositions. He used the computational power of the computer to determine compositional procedures such as the distribution of notes [4] [5]. Also, the resulting scores were played by classical instruments. The process of Xenakis' work made it clear that the computer provided aid to the composer and didn't produce the final composition. In contrast to Hiller, who regarded that a possible inadequacy of the algorithm to produce a satisfying result, must lead to the modification of the algorithm [5]. Another case of stochastic composition is the work of Karlheinz Stockhausen, *Klavierstück XI*. In this piece, Stockhausen was inspired by nature and chaos theory, resulting in the application of nonlinear dynamics equations to the composition where performers play fragments of music

in random sequence [4].

2.2.3 AI Era

One of the recent developments in algorithmic music composition is the incorporation of artificial intelligence. During the last couple of decades, various systems have been developed that are defining their own rules by their ability to learn [4]. Inspired by linguistics and computer science, multiple approaches have been applied such as evolutionary algorithms, neural networks, stochastic methods, generative models, agents, decision trees, declarative programming and grammars [7]. However, some of these systems are prone to limitations since they rely on a significant amount of data to function or they imitate composers [5]. According to Fernández et al [8], a grammar may be defined as a set of rules to expand high-level symbols into more detailed sequences of symbols (words) representing elements of formal languages. An early example of a simplistic rhythm generation using grammars was that of Lidov and Gabura in 1973 [8]. In addition, a book published in 1983 that didn't examine algorithmic composition had a significant impact on it, due to its immense popularity. Lerdahl et al work of *Generative Theory of Tonal Music* which presents a system of tonal analysis of music in grammatical terms inspired plentiful works of grammar-based systems. Furthermore, various, knowledge-based systems were developed since Hiller's *Illiac Suite* was presented. For example, Minsky in the late '70s and early '80s, established multiple paradigms to encode a set of constraints that solved specific problems. One of the most notable was *Society of Mind (SOM)* which influenced the work of multiple researchers [8]. Moreover, Thomas in 1985 designed in Lisp a four-part chorale for harmonization, while later in 1998 Riecken developed a system that generated monophonic melodies derived from specific emotional criteria chosen by the user [8]. During the 1980s and 1990s, logic programming became very popular in the research of algorithmic composition. Specifically, the paradigm of formulation of algorithmic composition tasks as constraint satisfaction problems (CSPs) was popular, and constraint logic programming (CLP) was the prominent solution to it [8]. One of the most notable researchers was Ebcioğlu who in 1988 developed CHORAL, a harmonization and melody generation system. A

very important and widespread method in the algorithmic music composition of the last couple of decades was the use of Markov Models. It is a memoryless stochastic process that models randomly changing systems and can be found in multiple researchers' work, for example, Tipei's (1975), Jones' (1981), Langston's (1989) and more recently Visell's (2004) work where he used the concept to implement a manual real-time generative system [8]. A notably refined approach to Markovian models was Pachet's (2002) real-time interactive music system, Continuator [8]. Also, a more contemporary method based on Markov models is FlowComposer by Papadopoulos et al presented in 2016. This system is a web application for musical lead sheets that generates melodic sequences [7]. In conclusion, the current state of algorithmic music composition consists mainly of implementations of deep learning algorithms, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN). Deep learning is a part of machine learning which is a family of mathematical models based on sample data, known as "training data", that make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to do so [9]. As computation power has risen over the past two decades, the implementation of machine learning has revolutionized multiple aspects of human life. Therefore, it was impossible to avoid its application in algorithmic composition. Examples include this of Grachten Chacón [10] who used a CNN in 2015 to produce a randomized process derived from exchanged datasets in the training process [7]. Another case of applied deep learning was that of Huang and Wu (2016) who constructed, using LSTM algorithms (a type of RNN), sophisticated musical structures. Likewise, Chu et al [11] produced a melody generation system that employs a type of RNN called Hierarchical Recurrent Network (HRN). Finally, G. Hadjeres and F. Pachet [12] presented a notable experiment in 2016. The DeepBach project was a system that generated credible polyphonic compositions derived from Bach Chorales.

2.3 Algorithmic Composition Systems

In this chapter, we will present a taxonomy of the methods that are currently applied in algorithmic music composition based on the work of Lopez-Rincon et al [7]. taxonomy table of the methods can be seen below. For each method, we describe the algorithmic process and present an example of an implementation in algorithmic music composition.

- Soft computing based music composition methods
 - Heuristic Composition Methods
 - * Evolutionary Algorithms
 - * Dynamic Programming
 - Deep Learning Composition Methods
 - * Deep Belief Networks
 - * Convolutional Networks
 - * Recurrent Networks
 - Stochastic Composition Methods
 - * Markov Models
 - * Generative Adversarial Networks
- Symbolic AI-based music composition methods
 - Agent Composition Methods
 - Declarative Programming Composition Methods
 - Grammar Composition Methods

Also, we should take into account that there are hybrid systems which use a combination of the reported techniques.

2.3.1 Evolutionary Algorithms

Evolutionary algorithms are a family of optimization algorithms inspired by biological evolution. They have a metaheuristic or stochastic function and they are used for problem-solving based in trial and error [13]. Specifically, they produce “populations” or possible sets of solutions, iteratively. In each new generation, the less desired characteristics are removed and random changes are applied. Therefore, the evolution of the population will result in the final chosen fitness function of the algorithm [13]. A subset of evolutionary algorithms is genetic algorithms, where compositions form the populations and the solution of the fitness function takes place through human interaction, an example of this method can be found at the work of Kaliakatsos–Papakostas et al [14] [7].

2.3.2 Dynamic Programming

Dynamic programming is an optimization method in programming that has multiple applications. It is a recursive way of solving complex problems by dividing them into smaller and simpler ones and seeking for their optimal solutions [15]. An example of dynamic programming applied to algorithmic music composition can be seen in the work of Fukayama et al [16] [7]. The researchers developed a system that generated automatic music composition derived from the Japanese language and lyrics, by complying to specific constraints that divide the lyrics [7]. As a result, dynamic programming produces the allocation of the syllables.

2.3.3 Deep Belief Networks

Deep belief networks (DBN) are probabilistic generative models that contain multiple layers of latent variables that are called “hidden units” [17]. The top two layers of the networks form an associative memory and have connections between them that are symmetrical and undirected. In unsupervised learning, DBNs can reconstruct their inputs in which the layers function as feature detectors and in the next step of supervised learning they can implement classification processes [17]. A case of implementation of DBNs in algorithmic composition can be identified in the research

work of Bickerman et al [18], where a dataset of four-bar jazz melodies was used to generate melodies [7].

2.3.4 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are deep learning algorithms that can use as an input most commonly images, attribute weights in certain parts of these images and then perform image recognition or classification. Their architecture is inspired by the neurons in the human brain and the organization of the visual cortex. A case of CNN implementation in algorithmic composition can be found in the previously mentioned research of Grachten Chacón [10], where they experimented with coding, decoding and prediction of a dataset. In their work, notes are represented as pixels to be used as an input in the CNN [7].

2.3.5 Recurrent Neural Networks

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are a category of artificial neural networks whereas inputs, outputs are used from previous steps with the help of hidden layers. Thus, information is kept (as memory) from internal states to process sequences of inputs [19]. In traditional neural networks, inputs and outputs are independent but for certain prediction tasks, RNNs are very effective since they use sequential information. Therefore, since they perform well in tasks applied in every element of a sequence that is depended on previous states, their application in music was inevitable. Specifically, a certain type of architecture called Long short-term memory (LSTM) is very popular in recent works of algorithmic music composition. For example, Lyu et al [20] proposed an automatic music generation model that memorizes and retrieves information and generates polyphonic music.

2.3.6 Markov Models

In probability theory, Markov models, named after their creator, are a stochastic method for randomly changing systems where it is assumed that future states do not depend on past states [21]. These models show all possible states as well as

the transitions, rate of transitions and probabilities between them. Markov Models are a memoryless system that consists of some finite number of discrete states and they are highly dependent on the transition probabilities between those states [21]. They are often used to model the probabilities of different states and the rates of transitions among them, hence the reason that they are consistently used in multiple approaches throughout the history of algorithmic composition, the probabilities of different states might represent notes, chords or other compositional processes. For example, Makris et al [19] used a type of Markov model called Markov chain, to build a system for improvisation that uses harmonic structures to generate probabilistic voice leads in melodic harmonization [7]. Another class of Markov models is Hidden Markov models (HMMs) which are used frequently too. In this case, the model assumes that there is a hidden state in which a current state depends on, therefore, the use of HMM is very effective in calculations of probable notes or chords such as, for example, in Eigenfeldt's et al work [22] [7] where an HMM calculates probability values for bass voicing.

2.3.7 Generative Adversarial Networks

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) are a machine learning architecture that was introduced in 2014 by Ian Goodfellow. In this framework, two neural networks compete with each other to generate new data that can be considered as real. Also, GANs are an approach to generative modelling where a supervised learning problem is divided into two parts, the generator model that generates new examples and the discriminator that performs classification between real or fake examples. As a result, their ability to generate new content turns them into useful tools for music generation as in the work of Yu et al [23] [7].

2.3.8 Agent Composition Methods

An agent refers to anything capable of perceiving an affordance and adequate to act upon its corresponding artefact [24] while an intelligent agent is capable of making decisions based on experience. In artificial intelligence, an autonomous intelligent

agent is a free entity that chooses between actions and upon observations to achieve goals. Their complexity varies and they can also exist in a multi-agent system of multiple interacting intelligent agents that can find solutions in high difficulty problems. An example of such a problem is the work of Navarro et al [25] where a multi-agent system that includes human interaction generates composition [7]. It contains a harmony searching algorithm which chooses an optimization function, considers probabilistically pitch and harmony memory and finally based on constraining rules it generates the composition.

2.3.9 Declarative Programming Composition Methods

Declarative programming is an approach to computer programming in which the programs state only their ultimate goal without describing the intermediary steps to reach it [3], therefore, they are context-independent, unlike imperative programming that often depends on the context. A case of declarative programming in algorithmic composition can be identified in the work of Eppe et al [26] in which the proposed system blends jazz chords. By using certain rules in regards to cadences, diatonicity and dissonance the system searches for chord combinations to complete cadences [7].

2.3.10 Grammar Composition Methods

In linguistics, a grammar is defined as the set of all the grammatical rules that determines the oral and written speech of a language. There are many different kinds of grammars, for instance, generative grammars which are “a precisely formulated set of rules whose output is all (and only) the sentences of a language” [27]. Also, they do not differentiate the grammatical sentence of a language from ungrammatical sequences of words [27]. In music, according to Steedman (2016) [8] “The idea that there is a grammar of music is probably as old as the idea of grammar itself”. Therefore, there have been developed several systems over the years that attempted to understand the musical styles of compositions by using grammars. A promising attempt is illustrated in the proposal of Quick Hudak [28] in which they present

a new category of a generative graph grammar for generating abstract harmonic and metrical structure [7]. These types of grammars have features that allow the expression of metrical structure of composition and also the sharing and repetition of specific musical phrases. Consequently, the authors define the class of grammars and implement it by presenting an example tailored to some styles of classical western music [28].

2.4 Automatic Melodic Harmonization

The purpose of this work is automatic melodic harmonization. But what is the relationship between automatic melodic harmonization and algorithmic music composition? At this point, we will try to define every concept of the task to arrive to the affiliation. In music, melody has been described in several ways. For instance, a parade of notes, one following the other meaningfully or for example an organized succession of pitches. Other definitions interpret melody as a succession of tones comprised of mode, rhythm, and pitches so arranged as to achieve musical shape, being perceived as a unity by the mind, or as a succession of notes of varying pitch, which form a recognizable musical shape. But all the attempts to define the nature of melody tend to converge in the use of the word satisfying. However, what does this satisfaction mean? melody is a musically satisfying sequence of notes and this satisfaction is related to harmony. The broader definition of harmony includes the combination of simultaneous musical notes or for instance the structure of music with respect to the composition and progression of chords [29]. A chord is any harmonic set of three or more notes that is heard as if sounding simultaneously (Benward Saker, 2003) and are typically consisting of four voices ranging from a higher to lower pitch: Soprano, Alto, Tenor, and Bass [29]. However, the narrower definition of harmony is a set of rules. Harmony refers to a system of principles that according to the relations between notes and chords are established. The study of harmony includes chords and their construction and extends to the development of chord progressions [29]. The role of harmony is considered to accompany the melody while also it is referred to as the "vertical" aspect of music where the "horizontal"

one is the melody. Therefore, the assignment of musical chords in a given melody is called melodic harmonization [29]. The melody harmonization task involves maintaining balance between the melody and all the chord-composing sequences [29]. This is accomplished by a collection of musical "rules" that describes a certain type of music, such as classical, rock, jazz etc. Traditionally, harmonic analysis is executed by musicians but computers enabled research to systematically investigate the framework of harmony. Also, the process of constructing the automated framework of harmony and capture the rules the harmonic analysis has been a goal of computer science since the 1960s [29]. Until now, automatic melodic harmonization has been approached from two main separate perspectives [29], in terms of harmonic analysis. The first one involves the attempt to assign a chord sequence to a given melody in a satisfactory way, usually, this voice is the soprano (higher one). This operation is traditionally done in the context of Western classical education. The second approach almost involves the reverse process, meaning, the search of the three remaining melodic lines given a bass one [29]. In conclusion, automatic melodic harmonization is the assignment of musical chords over a given melody [29] and in either case, it can be considered a sub-task of automatic music generation [30] and consequently, a branch of algorithmic music composition.

2.5 Automatic Melodic Harmonization System Types

Automatic melodic harmonization is a challenging task due to a lot of facts. Mainly because there are numerous ways to approach the implementation of the harmonic analysis but also because of all the subtleties of harmony that are difficult to perceive computationally [34]. Moreover, another factor is the subjectivity of satisfaction and that a particular harmonization might appear correct but at the same time unimaginative or monotonous. At this point, we will describe the most prominent automatic melodic harmonization systems based on the work of Makris et al [29]. One can easily observe that the systems are a subset of the systems used in algorithmic music composition. A list of the automatic melodic harmonization system types described in this part can be found below.

- Grammars
- Rule-based systems
- Genetic Algorithms
- Markov Models
- Machine learning and Hybrid approaches

2.5.1 Grammars

The amount of rules in harmony combined with their complexity led to the adoption of grammars by researchers as a reasonable solution to the problem of automatic melodic harmonization [29] since the 1960's. One of the first proposals was that of Winograd in 1968 where it was expected by the user to remove manually non-harmonic notes before the algorithm processed the remaining chord sequence [29]. Furthermore, Steedman experimented in 1984 with a context-free grammar for chord progressions in jazz twelve-bar blues and in 1996 he used categorical grammars, by putting into the lexicon the majority of the information that is captured in context-free phrase-structure rules [29]. Nonetheless, systems developed with grammars frequently have experience ambiguity problems. As a result, parsing symbolic information is very expensive. Moreover, regularly the quality of the generated results is controversial, thus a significant concern [29].

2.5.2 Rule-based systems

Rule-based or Knowledge-Based Systems use symbolic information along with rules and constraints to perform the task of automatic melodic harmonization. Before machine learning systems, they played a significant role in the research of the task. One of the first approaches of the task was that of Higgins Steedman in 1971 where they tried to deduce the tonality given a fugue melody from Bach's Well-Tempered Clavier. They used heuristic rules blended with elimination process. Two solutions were proposed one that determines metrical units and another one that determines harmonic relationships between notes, while the results were promising.

Another attempt developing a rule-based system was the one by Ebcioğlu in 1988 that was mentioned previously. He designed a 270-rule harmonizing system for four-part chorales in the style of J.S. Bach. The system was called CHORAL and was written in the logic program language BSL [29]. Furthermore, it used back trackable process techniques to implement multiple viewpoints [29] and the overall results confirmed the satisfactory operation of the system.

2.5.3 Genetic Algorithms

The use of genetic algorithms in composition is regarded promising since they can explore a large search space with constraints, thus the creativity derived from the exploration ability is governed by the fitness function. An early example of the implementation was that of Horner Ayers in 1995 where they used a genetic algorithm system to harmonize four-part complex musical progressions by separating the task into to subtasks. The first one found all the possible chord progressions and the second one identified chords that were appropriate for the voice leading. Finally, the application of the genetic algorithm led to the satisfactory solution of the chord sequencing problem apart from the fact that the problem was very constrained since all the chords were given as an input. Another experiment of using genetic algorithms to perform automatic melodic harmonization was that of Towsey et al in 2001 where they attempted to describe and solve the problem of definition of fitness functions that capture the aesthetic qualities of the wide range of successful melodies [29]. The genetic algorithm's fitness function was described by 21 melodic features and also 36 melodies were used for mutation procedures. Eventually, they concluded that it is impossible to draw strong conclusions from their dataset's cluster analysis.

2.5.4 Markov Models

One of the most common systems for harmonization is that of incorporating Markov models. In various systems, three Markov models were used widely based on whether every sequential state is observable or not and if the structure is to be modified based on observations made Markov Chain, Markov Decision Process and Hidden Markov

Models [29]. A Markov chain is a mathematical system that experiences transitions from one state to another according to certain probabilistic rules. A Markov decision process (MDP) is a discrete-time stochastic control process. It provides a mathematical framework for modelling decision making in situations where outcomes are partly random and partly under the control of a decision-maker [35]. Lastly, Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) that were mentioned previously are statistical Markov models in which the system that is being modelled is assumed to be a Markov process with unobserved (hidden) states (Eddy, 1998) [29]. HMMs are extensively used in automatic melodic harmonization. One example of an attempt using HMMs is this of Raphael and Stoddard in 2003. They proposed a probabilistic approach to functional harmonic analysis where the trained data using a collection of MIDI files in regards to rhythm and pitch [29]. Despite the simplifying assumptions and the reduction of parameters the results were not satisfying enough. Another instance of HMM incorporation was that of Allan and Williams in 2005 with the ultimate goal of the creation of a system that predicts notes for filling three voices. They proposed a four-part harmonization system built with two HMMs that generated chorales in the style of J.S. Bach. The first HMM produced a sequence of note intervals that accompanied each melody beat and at the same time, the second HMM produced ornamentations. The HMMs learned the probabilities using their training data set of harmonizations. Furthermore, a case of Markov Decision Process implementation was that of Yi et al [29] in 2007 where they developed a decision-theoretic planning system for chord progression generation. They represented states by utilizing tuples of voices and temporal positions. Ultimately, the results of harmonization were not sophisticated enough but the attempt was regarded positive in general, as it was proven that the application of this technique was possible.

2.5.5 Machine learning and hybrid approaches

Hybrid approaches (a combination of systems) along with machine learning task regarding the task of automatic melodic harmonization, tend to overcome the problem of ignoring certain variables that HMMs usually do. For example, tonality, scale or metric structure are usually not taken into account in previously mentioned systems,

thus they fail to capture essential aspects of musical structure and context and they are limited especially in regards to musically trained users. An early example of a hybrid system in 1999 was that of Cunha et al [29] that was built for chord prediction. It incorporated a neural net combined with a rule-based tracker that resulted in a promising outcome. Another approach in 2005 was presented by Dixon et al by using Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBN) which are graphical models representing a succession of simple Bayesian networks in time [29]. They proved that accuracy improvements of harmonization are possible by combining two modelling approaches, one of a chord transcription system that used a high-level model of musical context integrated with a Bayesian framework and another for learning logical descriptions of harmonic sequences by using logic programming [29]. Moreover, Paiement et al. proposed a graphical model that captures the chord structures in a given musical style in 2005 [29]. They used Expectation-maximization algorithm, the classical Junction Tree algorithm and a simple dynamical HMM and eventually concluded that they can improve the capture of chord progressions. Furthermore, Chuan et al in 2007 presented a hybrid harmonizing system in which Support Vector Machines (SVMs) were applied to generate from a given melody style-specific accompaniment [29]. The system determined chord tones, it assigned triads and finally constructed chord progressions using neo-Riemannian transforms. Additionally, Raczynski et al in 2013 presented a system that could develop discriminative probabilistic harmonization. The system joined multiple simpler sub-models (tonality, melody and the chord bigram model) employing linear or log-linear interpolation and trained them with satisfactory results. Finally, Suzuki and Kitahara in 2013 presented an investigation of what extent harmonization was affected by a model without chord notes compared to the one that contained them. They used Bayesian networks to develop a computational model which accomplished harmonization.

2.6 Contemporary Approaches on Automatic Melodic Harmonization

In recent years, the eruption of machine learning in numerous areas of human life has brought profound changes in the landscape of algorithmic music composition and more specifically melodic harmonization and generation of chord progressions. Most research on this subject involves the use of neural networks. For example, in 2016 Choi et al [31] proposed a method of text-based LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) networks for automatic music composition that can be used for fully automatic composition or as semi-automatic systems. The system can be used to generate symbolic chord sequences [31]. Also, Lim et al, introduced in 2017 a novel method of generating chord sequences from a symbolic melody using bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTM) networks trained on a lead sheet database [32]. The system extracts notes from each bar of melody, key and time are normalized and then the BLSTM networks are trained to generate a chord progression. As a result, the evaluations suggested better performance compared to conventional approaches as HMMs. A further study by Kaliakatsos-Papakostas et in 2017 proposed a creative melodic harmonization assistant that operates with statistical learning to learn harmonies from human-annotated data in any style [33]. The system integrates the harmonies of two user-selected idioms and harmonizes the melodies. The authors claim that the system expresses creatively the harmonic character of varied idioms and that the blended harmonies adequately create new harmonic concepts. Finally, a comparative study published in 2020 by Yeh et al that incorporated multiple approaches for automatic melodic harmonization with triad chords suggested a hybrid model that combines genetic algorithm and deep learning as promising. Specifically, the study included a template matching based model, a hidden Markov based model, a genetic algorithm-based model, and two deep learning-based models and the evaluation was conducted on a dataset of 9,226 melody/chord pairs and various metrics for standardized evaluation.

2.7 Conclusion of the State of the Art

Artificial intelligence (AI) is predestinated to become the most significant and defining technology of the 21st century. Besides algorithms that can perform complex tasks flawlessly, autonomous vehicles and applications to every possible sector from marketing to banking and even agriculture, AI has already expanded in creative industries. As a result, commercial systems have already been widely adopted on tasks related to music composition, production or autonomous music generation. Aiva, (stands for Artificial Intelligence Virtual Artist) is a commercial AI music composer capable of composing emotional soundtracks for films, video games, commercials and any type of entertainment content and can assist composers on their creative process. Flow Machines, developed in Sony Computer Science Laboratories, is a system developed for autonomous music generation of a broad range of musical styles, with or without the collaboration of human artists. Finally, Google's magenta is an open-source research project exploring the role of machine learning as a tool in the creative process. It pushes the limits of AI's abilities in the process of music and art creation and it provides tools to experiment, for everyone. In conclusion, the music composition landscape has changed dramatically and definitively with the advent of AI. Although most of the innovative research takes place in research centers, accessible software has been made available to the general public with great acceptance, resulting in more relevant research that has changed music composition forever.

2.8 Objectives

In this work, we will attempt to provide a proof of concept of the work of Lim et al [32] on chord generation from symbolic melody using BLSTM networks with some differentiations which we believe that potentially can improve the model. The work of the authors was published in 2017 and provided a novel method of generating chord sequences from symbolic melody. The method of their experiment was robust and reasonably designed while the theoretical support of it was comprehensive. However, the model contains some limitations that we would like to consider

and ideally resolve. The proposal of this thesis follows a similar model architecture to the work to which we refer to but with differentiations related to melodic and harmonic generalizations, assumptions and particularly alterations of the predicted vector outputs. In conclusion, the work of Lim et al [32] will provide the foundation of this thesis which will attempt to explore new territories in the implementation of automatic melodic harmonization. For the purpose of this work, we would like to note that the terms “automatic melodic harmonization” and “chord generation from melody” are used interchangeably. We acknowledge the technical differences that might occur but we consider them identical in the context of this work

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Overview

3.1.1 Reference

In this part of the thesis, we will explain the overall methodology of the referenced work of Lim et al [32] and we will describe our proposal. The method proposed by the authors consists of two parts, the preprocessing procedure and the model training with chord generation. In the preprocessing part, authors analyse the dataset and transpose all tracks to C major key for data consistency and normalization. In addition, the variety of time signature creates an imbalance of note durations, therefore they are multiplied with reciprocal numbers in order to be normalized. Subsequently, the musical features are extracted from the lead sheets such as time signature, bars, key signature, chords and notes [32]. The majority of the bars in the lead sheets have a single chord per bar but if a bar consists of two or more chords, the authors choose the first chord in the bar. Moreover, a matrix of concatenating rows is constructed. Every row of the matrix represents a single note and every column represents the features mentioned above. An example of extracted data of a single bar can be seen in Figure 2.

Furthermore, twelve semitone classes represent a note in a bar without octave in-

time	measure	key_fifths	key_mode	chord_root	chord_type	note_root	note_octave	note_duration
4/4	1	-1	major	F0	major	A0	4	8.0
4/4	1	-1	major	F0	major	rest	0	2.0
4/4	1	-1	major	F0	major	A0	4	2.0
4/4	1	-1	major	F0	major	G0	4	2.0
4/4	1	-1	major	F0	major	F0	4	2.0

Figure 2: Extracted data of a single bar

formation and each of these classes consists of a single value that accumulates the duration of the corresponding semitone in the bar. Finally, the authors chose to map all types of possible chords into major or minor triads claiming that since the total number of chord types is quite large, all those independent classes will result in few chord samples. Therefore, they represent every chord (24 major and minor chords) with a binary 24-dimensional class.

In the second part of the work, authors apply a BLSTM network. They argue that the choice of this particular method is efficient enough since the network can reflect musical context not only in forward but also in backward directions [32]. As a result, input semitone vectors are constructed from each bar and used as an input of the network, in sequence during the time step and for a fixed number of bars. In order to train the sequence of multiple bars, the authors apply a window with the size of the time step and overlapping the window with the hop size of one bar. Each window of multiple bars is used as a sample to train the network. Consequently, the network generates output chord classes in the order of the input. An overview of their system can be seen in Figure 3.

The authors use hyperbolic tangent activation function for the hidden layers to

Figure 3: Referenced paper's system

reconstruct the features in a nonlinear process and afterwards apply the softmax function for the output layer to generate values of the probability of each class. In addition, a dropout of 0.2 is used on all hidden layers to prevent overfitting. Also, mini-batch gradient descent with categorical cross-entropy is used as the cost function and Adam as the optimizer. Finally, a batch size of 512 and early stopping for 10 epoch patience is used for the training.

3.1.2 Proposal

In this part of the thesis, we will describe in detail our proposal and differentiation for the proof of concept of the work of Lim et al [32]. We will describe the main differentiation of our approach compared to the referenced work and it can be considered that the remaining parts will be followed accordingly, as described earlier in the methodology overview of our reference. Firstly, the extraction process of the meaningful musical information of data will take place similarly but not identically. Therefore, we propose a massive transposition of the dataset to C major and minor according to the initial key signature of a track, for data consistency and normalization. We consider the choice of a unique key signature (major) and the elimination of others limited, in terms of musicality and we believe that in our approach of not discriminating between key signatures, the melodic and harmonic information will be implied in our data inputs and outputs. Secondly, our main differentiation from the reference is this of the chord representation in the output of the model. Primarily, we consider the authors' mapping of all possible chords into major or minor triads and the representation of only 12 major and 12 minor chords very limiting. Therefore, we propose a different approach where a chord is represented by 8 note classes. We chose this number as this is the maximum number of simultaneous notes on a chord in the dataset. As a result, a chord will be detected from an example, it will get analysed and represented by a 12-value vector of the classes of note occurrences that will contain a maximum of 8 note classes in every chord. For example, a C major chord will be represented by a vector of numbers where the three classes of C, E and G will be 1 and the other nine will be zero. Consequently, the result of the prediction of the model might leave room for applications that consist of richer

chord suggestions and possibly music genre conditioning. An overview of our system proposal can be seen in Figure 4 and also a more detailed view of the input/output layers of both systems in Appendix A .

Figure 4: Our proposed system

3.2 Dataset

In this work, we use the same dataset as Lim et al [32] in the referenced work. Specifically, we use the public lead sheet database provided by Wikifonia.org. The data consists of 6,675 Western music lead sheets in various music genres such as rock, pop, country, jazz, folk, RB etc. Also, we take advantage of the dataset's format which is musicXML. This type of file is an XML-based file format for representing Western musical notation that allows easy extraction and manipulation of musical data. It is designed for sharing sheet music files between applications, and for archiving sheet music files. In addition, it turns the establishment of a relation between melody and harmony a convenient and straightforward process. In other words, all these features mentioned above make this dataset ideal in the case of our research. The dataset can be found on the website of the referenced authors where they present their results. (http://marg.snu.ac.kr/chord_generation/)

3.3 Information extraction and data manipulation

In this part, we will describe the extraction and processing of the raw data in the order in which it was subjected. The desired and final result of this step of the process is a data frame containing concatenated rows that represent sequential notes of the tracks. To achieve this goal, the programming language python is used along with music21, which is a Python-based toolkit for computer-aided musicology that is commonly used for musicological research and study of large datasets of music. In the first step of the process, an initial audit of the dataset takes place which separates the useful files from the useless or the broken ones. This distinction takes into account the file type (some types are unrecognizable or contain errors) while checks whether the prerequisite of the existence of notes alongside with chords is satisfied, meaning that the file should contain notes and chords at the same time. From this process, it emerged that the number of files that can be used for extraction is 5968. Every other file that didn't satisfy the condition was discarded from the dataset. In the next step, the usable files undergo a basic analysis. From

this analysis time and key signature is extracted. Specifically, the time signature is easy to extract as it is included, raw in every file. On the other hand, the key signature is not so easily detected. It might be included in the information of each musicXML file but its accuracy is potentially debatable. Also, the option of music21 analysis is available but again its accuracy is questionable. Therefore, we construct a simple algorithm that increases the chances of accurate key signature detection. This simple algorithm detects only chords since their harmonic information is more robust than melody, it itemizes them, appends them in a music stream and finally analyses them to determine the key signature. From this analysis, it emerged that all the possible (24) major and minor scales are included in the dataset. After the detection of time and key signature, a data frame is built that contains as rows the name of each file and as columns the detected information. Furthermore, another analysis is implemented that eliminates additional files that contain errors such as files with multiple instruments that contain exclusively rests. The final number of usable files is 5942. The final step of the data extraction incorporates a deeper analysis and manipulation in note level that results in the construction of our final data frame. This final data frame contains concatenated note information as rows for every track in the dataset. Firstly, every usable file is analysed bar by bar where for each note a row is constructed that contains the initial information below:

Note	Chord Pitch Numerical Classes	Chord Note 3
Midi Note	Chord Inversion	Chord Note 4
Note Pitch Class	Duration	Chord Note 5
Note Pitch Numerical Class	Bar	Chord Note 6
Octave	Beat Position	Chord Note 7
Chord	Chord Note 1	Chord Note 8
Chord Pitch Classes	Chord Note 2	

Table 1: Features extracted from the dataset

The bars that might not contain notes alongside with chords, are discarded. In total, 18 features are present in the data frame. Finally, the key signature of each file is retrieved from the first data frame that contained the basic file information. The key signature retrieved is processed by an algorithm that determines the amount

of semitones needed in order to transpose each track’s rows to C major or C minor. Consequently, the musical information of each row is modified according to transposition to our desirable key signature. Ultimately, a large data frame is built containing 925.223 concatenated rows that represent sequential notes derived from every usable track in the dataset, transposed to C major or minor. An overview of the data frame can be viewed in Figure 5.

MainDataFrame																		
	Transposed Note Pitch Numerical Class	Octave	Duration	Bar	Beat Position	Key Major	Key Minor	Time Signature Numerator	Time Signature Denominator	Chord Inversion	Chord Note 1	Chord Note 2	Chord Note 3	Chord Note 4	Chord Note 5	Chord Note 6	Chord Note 7	Chord Note 8
0	4	4	1	1	1	1	0	3	4	0	4	7	11	12	12	12	12	12
1	6	4	1.5	1	2	1	0	3	4	0	4	7	11	12	12	12	12	12
2	7	4	0.5	1	3.5	1	0	3	4	0	4	7	11	12	12	12	12	12
3	11	4	3	2	1	1	0	3	4	0	0	4	7	10	2	12	12	12
4	4	4	1	3	1	1	0	3	4	0	4	7	11	12	12	12	12	12
...
925218	4	4	2	33	1	1	0	4	4	0	7	11	2	5	12	12	12	12
925219	7	4	2	33	3	1	0	4	4	0	7	11	2	5	12	12	12	12
925220	0	5	4	34	1	1	0	4	4	0	0	4	7	12	12	12	12	12
925221	0	5	2	35	1	1	0	4	4	0	0	4	7	12	12	12	12	12
925222	12	0	2	35	3	1	0	4	4	0	0	4	7	12	12	12	12	12

925223 rows × 18 columns

Figure 5: Our data frame

3.4 Model

Nowadays, deep learning techniques have exceeded previous approaches in terms of performance, especially in machine learning tasks of large datasets [32]. Specifically, for temporal sequences, recurrent neural networks (RNN) have been proven to achieve greater accuracy compared to preceding models such as hidden Markov models (HMM). Moreover, long short term memory (LSTM) networks have demonstrated strong evidence of their predominance in tasks that incorporate temporal sequences. Currently, they are widely used in multiple fields as well as music research relevant to music sequence generation or music component generation [32].

In this work, we will attempt to implement an automatic melodic harmonization system from symbolic melody using bidirectional LSTM networks, where a symbolic melody will be used as an input and predicted note classes that compose a chord

will constitute the output.

3.4.1 Bidirectional LSTM

Recurrent neural network (RNN) is a class of artificial neural networks where connections between nodes form a directed graph along a temporal sequence. This allows it to exhibit temporal dynamic behavior. Derived from feedforward neural networks, RNNs can use their internal state (memory) to process variable length sequences of inputs [40]. This quality makes them applicable to a variety of problems such as speech recognition, language modeling, translation, image captioning etc. In RNNs the number of feedback on a recurrent process is controlled by timestep [32]. By storing past information in the internal memory, RNNs incorporate temporal dependencies [32]. However, in theory, RNNs are capable of handling long-term dependencies but vanishing gradient during the back propagation through time (BPTT) causes problems [32]. As the number of hidden layers increases, the error between the estimated value and the actual value diminishes when calculating the gradient of the loss function. Long Short Term Memory networks are a special kind of RNN, capable of learning long-term dependencies and avoid the problem by remembering information for long periods of time. All recurrent neural networks have the form of a chain of repeating modules of neural network. In standard RNNs, this repeating module will have a very simple structure, such as a single tanh layer [42].

Bidirectional LSTMs are an extension of typical LSTMs that can enhance the performance of the model on sequence classification problems. BLSTMs train two instead of one LSTMs on the input sequence where all time steps of the input sequence are available. The first on the input sequence as it is and the other on a reversed copy of the input sequence. By this, additional context is added to network and learning results are faster. In addition, what differs this approach from unidirectional is that in the LSTM that runs backward information is preserved from the future and using the two hidden states combined we are able in any point in time to preserve information from both past and future. Therefore, in music related tasks such as melody or chord generation, sequential order is crucial and

Figure 6: BLSTM architecture

is affected by both previous and next order. Consequently, we apply BLSTM in order to preserve musical context in both forward and backward direction. The architecture of a BLSTM can be seen in figure 6.

3.4.2 BLSTM model description

Long Short Term Memory Recurrent Neural Networks (LSTM) have been proved to be a successful attempt to address the problem of the vanishing gradients for Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [34]. The architecture of LSTM includes memory blocks which are a set of recurrently connected subnets. Each block contains one or more self-connected memory cells and three multiplicative units - the input, output and forget gates - that provide continuous analogues of write, read and reset operations for the cells [34]. A LSTM network is formed exactly like a simple RNN, except that the nonlinear units in the hidden layers are replaced by memory blocks. The multiplicative gates allow LSTM memory cells to store and access information over long periods of time, thereby avoiding the vanishing gradient problem. For example, as long as the input gate remains closed (i.e. has an activation close to 0), the activation of the cell will not be overwritten by the new inputs arriving in the

network, and can therefore be made available to the net much later in the sequence, by opening the output gate [34]. Given an input sequence $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_T)$, a standard recurrent neural network (RNN) computes the hidden vector sequence $\mathbf{h} = (h_1, \dots, h_T)$ and output vector sequence $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_T)$ by iterating the following equations from $t = 1$ to T :

$$h_t = H(W_{x_h}x_t + W_{h_h}h_{t-1} + b_h)$$

$$y_t = W_{h_y}h_t + b_0$$

where the W terms denote weight matrices (e.g. W_{x_h} is the input-hidden weight matrix), the b terms denote bias vectors (e.g. b_h is the hidden bias vector) and H is the hidden layer function. H is usually an element wise application of a sigmoid function. However it has been found that the LSTM architecture [34], which uses custom-built memory cells to store information, is better at finding and exploiting long range context [34]. H is implemented as following.

$$i_t = \sigma(W_{x_i}x_t + W_{h_i}h_{t-1} + W_{c_i}c_{t-1} + b_i)$$

$$f_t = \sigma(W_{x_f}x_t + W_{h_f}h_{t-1} + W_{c_f}c_{t-1} + b_f)$$

$$c_t = f_t c_{t-1} + i_t \tanh(W_{x_c}x_t + W_{h_c}h_{t-1} + b_c)$$

$$o_t = \sigma(W_{x_o}x_t + W_{h_o}h_{t-1} + W_{c_o}c_t + b_o)$$

$$h_t = o_t \tanh(c_t)$$

where σ is the logistic sigmoid function, and i , f , o and c are respectively the input gate, forget gate, output gate and cell activation vectors, all of which are the same size as the hidden vector h [34]. W_{h_i} is the hidden-input gate matrix, W_{h_o} is the input-output gate matrix. The weight matrix from the cell to gate vectors (e.g. W_{c_i}) are diagonal, so element m in each gate vector only receives input from element m of the cell vector [34]. One shortcoming of conventional RNNs is that they are

only able to make use of previous context. Bidirectional RNNs (BRNNs) do this by processing the data in both directions with two separate hidden layers, which are then feed forwards to the same output layer. A BRNN computes the forward hidden sequence \vec{h} , the backward hidden sequence \overleftarrow{h} and the output sequence y by iterating the backward layer from $t = T$ to 1, the forward layer from $t = 1$ to T and then updating the output layer:

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{h}_t &= H(W_{x\vec{h}}x_t + W_{\vec{h}\vec{h}}\vec{h}_{t+1} + b_{\vec{h}}) \\ \overleftarrow{h}_t &= H(W_{x\overleftarrow{h}}x_t + W_{\overleftarrow{h}\overleftarrow{h}}\overleftarrow{h}_{t+1} + b_{\overleftarrow{h}}) \\ y_t &= W_{\vec{h}y}\vec{h}_t + W_{\overleftarrow{h}y}\overleftarrow{h}_t + b_y\end{aligned}$$

Combining BRNNs with LSTM gives bidirectional LSTM , which can access long-range context in both input directions [34].

3.4.3 Data pre-processing

In this part of the work, we will describe the data preprocessing operation that took place to build input and output vectors in a proper format to train our model. Firstly, as described in the data extraction part, to achieve homogeneity the whole data frame is transposed into C major or minor scales according to each track's tonality. Also, for consistency purposes the time signature is normalized. The variety of meters in our dataset produces an imbalance of note durations therefore, we multiply the time signature with the reciprocal number of each time signature. Making this assumption allows us to treat the data in a uniform time signature.

Secondly, to implement our model, the necessity of selecting a time resolution window arises. As a result, in our experiments, we choose the time signature of sixteenth notes. Consequently, all notes' duration is transformed into multiples of sixteenth notes and the notes that have a duration smaller than this time frame are generalized and considered of this duration. In fact, the amount of notes less than a 16th in our dataset is 3256 which we can consider insignificant since it constitutes 0.35%

of the total notes of our dataset that contains 925.223 notes.

Finally, the part of vectorization takes place. For the input layer of the model, we construct vectors of twelve units from every note of a four-bar sequence of the data frame. The vectors represent the twelve-note classes and enter the network sequentially. Since our time resolution window is the sixteenth note, the result of a four-bar sequence consists of a 64-row array, each of twelve binary units that represent the note classes accordingly. For the output layer, we construct vectors which represent the twelve binary classes of the notes that are used in one chord, with a maximum number of eight notes in a chord. The vectors's amount of rows correspond to the number of the bars extracted in the sequence, therefore their number will be four since in our work (specifically in the dataset that we use) each bar consists of one chord and the choice of our time resolution is four bars. You can observe the differences in input and output layer architecture between the referenced work and our proposal in figures 7 and 8 in appendix A.

3.4.4 Experiments

For our model, we run three different experiments of BLSTM of different settings with the ultimate goal of optimal performance for our model. In our first experiment, we build a time distributed input layer of 12 units, which represents the sequence of note classes vectors, 1 hidden layer with 20 BLSTM units, and a time distributed output layer with 12 units, which represents the chord note classes. To prevent overfitting dropout is employed with a rate of 0.2 on a hidden layer. In addition, we use binary cross-entropy as the cost function and Adam as the optimizer. Moreover, we use a batch size of 768 where the network weights are updated after each training example. In our next two experiments, we keep the same settings on the model but in the first case we use 64 BLSTM units and 2 hidden layers and in the second case 128 BLSTM units with also 2 hidden layers. The data set is split into an 80/20 ratio for the training and the testing part respectively.

Chapter 4

Evaluation

We perform a quantitative analysis by comparing the accuracies of the produced chord-vectors of our experiments with the accuracies of the two other models. The accuracy is calculated by counting the number of matching classes of our chord vector. As it was mentioned before, we apply a four-bar melody input sequence in our model and we expect an output sequence of four vectors that represent the 12 semitone classes of the notes that can be found on a chord. The first model we use for evaluation purposes is a simple LSTM, without the bidirectional layer. Long short-term memory (LSTMs) are artificial recurrent neural networks (RNNs) used in deep learning that has feedback connections. They can process entire sequences of data and they perform well in tasks such as classification and prediction of time series data. In our work, our main focus is Bidirectional LSTMs which are an extension of traditional LSTMs that can improve model performance on sequence classification problems. Therefore, the necessity of comparing the two models is strong to verify the advantage of an extra LSTM (in Bidirectional model) that is trained on the reversed copy of the input sequence. The second model that we use in this work for evaluation is a simple recurrent neural network (RNN). LSTMs are a type of RNN but with feedback connections. RNNs learn while training but also they remember things learnt from prior inputs while generating outputs [35]. RNNs can take one or more input vectors and produce one or more output vectors and the outputs are

influenced not just by weights applied on inputs like a regular neural network, but also by a “hidden” state vector representing the context based on prior inputs and outputs [35].

In both of the evaluation models, we maintain the same system of vector arrays and four-bar sequences of chords.

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 Overview

In this chapter, we present the results of the experiments that took place in our work. The table below presents the accuracy results of the three models for four-bar sequence lengths.

Model	Accuracy	SD
BLSTM Experiment 1	77,93%	6,58%
BLSTM Experiment 2	79,80%	5,62%
BLSTM Experiment 3	81,79%	6,52%
LSTM	86,05%	3,64%
RNN	81,14%	5,67%

Table 2: The results of the experiments along with the evaluation models

The results show that the LSTM method achieves the best performance on the test set followed by BLSTM experiment 3 and RNN. According to the average scores of models, BLSTM has 4.6% decrease from LSTM and 0.65% performance increase from the RNN, respectively.

Based on the results we observe that our model's accuracy improves as we increase the number of layers and units of the network. However, we were expecting that the BLSTM will perform better compared to other models in all of our experiments. This result may have occurred due to various factors. For example, the number

of bars used in our experiments ($b=4$) may be small so that the reverse sequence information may not be utilized in this time frame. In music, (assuming western European harmony in our context) what follows or precedes plays an important role in the melodic movement, therefore, the reverse sequence of the backward layer is expected to capture that fact.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 Conclusions

In this work, we attempted to provide a proof of concept of generating chord progressions using bidirectional long short-term memory (BLSTM) networks from symbolic melodies based on the work of Lim et al [32]. We introduced a different approach that can be divided into two parts. Firstly, we considered necessary to maintain both major and minor keys in our data manipulation process and secondly, we represented the chords in a different way. We constructed vectors which represent the twelve binary classes of the notes that are used in one chord, with a maximum number of eight notes in a chord. By this suggestion, we proposed that richer chord instances could arise from this execution. Our experiments showed that BLSTM's accuracy improved as the number of layers and units of the network were increasing. Moreover, more conventional algorithms used for evaluation performed a little better, possibly due to the fact that a four-bar sequence could have been limited as an input. Automatic melodic harmonization is a challenging task that requires taking into account multiple factors that will satisfy a state of the art implementation. Nevertheless, contemporary techniques of artificial recurrent neural networks implementation seem to perform well on the task.

6.2 Future work

In this work, there is enough room for further improvement which can be divided into three main parts.

First of all, more experiments can be conducted that can contain a different amount of consecutive bars as inputs. In our case, a four-bar sequence was used but it is debatable whether it was large enough to include adequate sequence information, therefore, an experiment that uses 8,12 or 16 bars could potentially give an answer to this question.

Secondly, an interesting improvement that can have more practical implications would be one of the construction of a dictionary that could “decode” the output of the model and generate specific chord suggestions. This procedure could be based on a variable which depending on its value could produce from simpler chords like major or minor triads to more complex ones.

Thirdly, an engaging improvement to this work would be the one of sound implementation. A library could be used in order to sonify the symbolic data so that the chord progression generation of the previous step can be listened to.

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Appendix A

First Appendix

Figure 7: Reference's input/output layers

Figure 8: Our proposed input/output layers